

Perception of Social Media Marketing among Teachers in a Private School in Chennai

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Abstract

Social media have provided various new opportunities to consumers to engage in social interaction through the internet. In today's technology driven world, the social networking sites have become a platform where the retailers can extend their marketing activities to a wider range of consumers. The study of social media marketing can also identify the advantages to be gained by the business. Hence this study attempts to understand the perception of teachers working in a private school in Chennai regarding the Social Media Marketing. The study found that there is a negative relationship between the socio demographic factors and the factors influencing the respondents to purchase through social media marketing.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing, perception

Meaning of Marketing

Marketing refers to those activities which a company undertakes to gain customers and maintain relationships with them. It also refers to those activities of a company that is associated with buying and selling of a product or service. People who work in companies in marketing departments try to get the attention of the target audiences using slogans, packaging design, celebrity endorsements and general media exposure.

Meaning of Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is the use of social media platforms and website in order to promote a product or service. This concept of social media marketing is becoming more popular for both practitioners and researchers. On a strategic level, social media marketing includes the management of a marketing campaign, governance, setting the scope and the establishment of a firm's desired social media "culture" and "tone."

Social media marketing (SMM) is the utilisation of social media websites and social networks to market and advertise an organization's products and services. Social media marketing provides companies with a way to approach new customers, engage with existing customers and promote its desired culture, mission or tone.

Social Media Marketing Strategy

A noteworthy technique used in social media marketing is to create messages and substance that individual clients will impart to their family, companions and collaborators. This approach relies on word of mouth and provides several benefits. First, it expands the message's reach to networks and users that a social media manager may not have been able to access otherwise. Second, shared content transmits an implicit endorsement when sent by someone who the recipient knows and trusts.

Social media strategy includes the making of content that is "sticky," meaning that it will stand out enough to be noticed and increase the possibility that a person will direct an anticipated action, such as purchase a product or share the content with their peers. Marketers create viral content intended to spread between users quickly. Social media marketing should ought to urge customers to create and share their own content, such as product reviews or comments (known as "earned media").

Statement of the Problem

In the modern era, much emphasis is given to social media. The older generation may not be willing to replace their traditional way of their living but the younger generations have transformed to a technology driven world. This study helps to identify the level of perception of social media marketing among the teachers at a private school in Chennai.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyse the perception of social media marketing among the teachers in a private school in Chennai
- To understand the teachers attitude towards social media marketing.
- To determine the factors influencing the teachers to prefer social media marketing.

Methodology

Source of data

Primary and Secondary data has been used for the study. Primary data was collected from the teachers of a private school in Chennai. Secondary data was collected from Newspaper, Journals, Magazines and the Internet.

Population

The population for this research includes teachers of a private school in Chennai which is 85.

Sample Size

The sample size taken for this research is 85, which represents the entire population of the total number of teachers working in a private school in Chennai.

Sampling Method

The sampling method adopted in this project is Convenient sampling.

Instrument Used

The main source of data was collected through primary data, which was collected through questionnaire with open and close ended questions. This questionnaire was prepared to elicit information regarding the teachers' perception of social media marketing and the factors influencing the teachers to prefer social media marketing.

Tools for analysis of data

The primary data collected has been analysed with the help of MS-Excel, through which ANOVA and Correlation Tests were employed to test the hypotheses framed for the study.

Hypotheses of the study

- i. There is no significant difference between the age of the respondents and their perception that social media marketing will help in their purchasing decision.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the age of the respondents and trustworthiness of the social media marketing.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between the stream of education and their perception that social media marketing will help in their purchasing decision.
- iv. There is no significant relationship between gender of the respondents and their opinion that social media marketing is making us a materialistic society.
- v. There is no significant relationship between age of the respondents and the influence of social media marketing in their shopping trend.

Review of Literature

Angella J. Kim, Eunju Ko¹, In light of a growing interest in the use of social media marketing (SMM) among luxury fashion brands, this investigation set out to distinguish qualities of SMM exercises and analyze the relationship among those perceived activities, value equity, relationship equity, brand equity, customer equity, and purchase intention through a structural equation model.. Five dimensions of perceived SMM exercises of luxury fashion brand are entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customisation and word of mouth. The study found that there is significant relationship between purchase intention and customer equity. It also revealed a negative effect of brand equity on customer equity whereas value equity and relationship equity had significant positive effects.

Christy Ashley, Tracy Tuten², conducted an investigation that utilized a content analysis of the creative strategies present in the social media shared by a sample of top brands. The outcomes uncover which social media channels are being utilized, which inventive systems/appeals are being utilized, and how these channels and techniques identify with customer commitment in branded social media. This investigation affirmed the significance of continuous updates and motivating forces for inducing customer interest. Likewise, a few inventive systems were related with client engagement, particularly experiential, pictorial, and personalised messages.

W. Glynn Mangold, David. J Faulds³, suggests that the development of Internet-based online networking has made it workable for one individual to speak with hundreds or even a large number of other individuals about the products offered by the organizations. In this manner, the effect of consumer-to-consumer correspondences has been extraordinarily increased in the market place. This article contends that internet based life is a amalgam component of the promotion mix in light of the fact that in a customary sense it empowers organizations to converse with their clients, while in a nontraditional sense it empowers clients to talk straightforwardly to each other.

Findings

Anova

Table 1
Table showing the age of the respondents and their perception that social media marketing will help in their purchasing decision

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value
Between Groups	5.05	1	6.5	7.612048	0.007221
Within Groups	51.5	89	1.532051		
Total	59.55	90			

Inference: The null hypothesis is rejected since the P value is lesser than 0.05 and hence there is a significant difference between age of the respondents and their perception that social media marketing will help in their purchasing decision.

Table 2
Table showing the age of the respondents and trustworthiness of the social media marketing

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value
Between Groups	1.45	1	2.45	0.681553	0.41151
Within Groups	61.5	89	1.660253		
Total	62.95	90			

Inference: The null hypothesis is accepted since the P value is greater than 0.05. So there is no significant difference between the age of the respondents and trustworthiness of the social media marketing.

Correlation Analysis

Table 3
Table showing the relationship between the stream of education and the purchase decision

	Stream of education	Help in Purchase Decision
Stream of education	1	
Help in Purchase decision	-0.14211	1

Inference: The above table represents that there is a negative correlation between the stream of education (Arts & Science) and perception that social media marketing will help in their purchasing decision.

Table 4
Table showing relationship between gender of the respondents and their opinion that social media marketing is making us a materialistic society.

	Gender	Creation of Materialistic society
Gender	1	
Creation of Materialistic society	-0.01151	1

Inference: It can be understood from the above table that there is a negative correlation between the gender of the respondents and their opinion that social media marketing will create a materialistic society.

Table 5
Table showing relationship between age of the respondents and the influence of social media marketing in their shopping trend

	Age	Influencing shopping trend
Age	1	
Influencing shopping trend	-0.32879	1

Inference: The above table depicts that there is a negative correlation between the age of the respondents and the influence of social media marketing in increasing their shopping trend.

Suggestions

1. Most important factor which motivates people to use the social networking sites is the presence of information exchange. Brands can use this motivator by promoting interesting facts about their brands and the alternate use of their products.
2. Consumers expect the social networking sites to be more secured which will even more motivate them to use more of social media marketing.
3. The social media marketing strategy must be flexible so that it can adapt to new developments and determine what works and what does not work.
4. It is important that the business must take time to learn how the social media marketing works for their specific business so that apt strategy can be used to get better results.
5. The reviews and complaints raised by the consumers should be effectively managed and proper and prompt actions must be taken so that the consumers will not be left unattended.

Conclusion

Online networking has turned into an indispensable piece of the calculations that choose where a specific site is put in the pursuit rankings. The higher the positioning the more unmistakable it is to the shopper. Since social media sites can be misused for the data it furnishes on consumer behaviour concerning their purchasing goals, need has been felt that organizations should fuse social media marketing into their plan of action in marketing their products. Social media sites are being used to improve an organization's image and widen their target market in light of the fact that new advancements take into account more individual, directed correspondences, and in addition expanded customer involvement in the formation of marketing and brand related information.

References

- Angella J. Kim & Eunju Ko, Do social media marketing activities enhance customer equity? An empirical study of luxury fashion brand, *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 65, no. 10, 2012, pp. 1480-1486.
- Christy Ashley & Tracy Tuten, Creative Strategies in Social Media Marketing: An Exploratory Study of Branded Social Content and Consumer Engagement, *Psychology and Marketing*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2015, pp. 15-27.
- Glynn Mangold, W. & David. J Faulds, Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix, *Business Horizons*, vol. 52, no. 4, 2009, pp. 357-365.